

IMPACTS OF SUPERCRITICAL FLUIDS ON THE MORPHOLOGY AND PERFORMANCE OF POLY(ETHER ETHER KETONE)

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ABSTRACT

The application of supercritical fluid (SCF) technology to high-performance polymers is becoming increasingly important as such polymers become more prevalent in industry. The response of fabricated parts to SCF environments can be critical to performance. This study examines the effects of absorption of SCFs on the crystallization behavior of poly(aryl ether ether ketone) [PEEK]. Special attention is given to the ability to induce different levels of crystallinity by exposing PEEK to chlorodifluoromethane at various supercritical conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Poly(aryl ether ether ketone) [PEEK] has warranted considerable commercial interest as a high-performance thermoplastic polymer. It has excellent thermal stability, is semicrystalline, tough and ductile, and exhibits excellent chemical resistance. The performance of PEEK and PEEK-based composites is often dependent upon the morphology of the polymer. This morphology is, in turn, dependent upon the thermal annealing cycle the material experiences during processing. PEEK is heavily considered with regard to many environments where particular thermal and chemical extremes prevail. Many times the tendency to use PEEK and PEEK-based composites in such situations may compromise performance. Furthermore, PEEK morphology may change with time during use in some applications due to exposure to high temperatures and/or solvents. These points raise viable concerns regarding PEEK's long-term environmental stability. The following study addresses the interaction between PEEK and supercritical fluids (SCFs) and examines the effect of such on the polymer's morphological changes.

Poly (aryl ether ether ketone) [PEEK] is an excellent model for the study of polymer morphology, environmental stability, durability and degradation. Many facets of this polymer's behavior have been extensively reported, including its synthesis [1], swelling [2], diffusion [3-5] and solubility [6-8]. Its crystalline morphology [9-10] and the ability to create such, be it thermally [11] or solvent-induced [12-14], has been reported. The mechanical properties of PEEK have also been reported [15].

When amorphous PEEK is heated from ambient temperature, its glass transition [16] occurs at about 145°C. An exothermic peak is observed at about 170°C, where crystallinity is produced to about 16%. With increasing temperature, crystallinity increases to a level of about 34% just before melting commences at 335°C. This latter crystallization is usually observed as a single broad peak, but two melting peaks can be developed to various degrees by annealing at different temperatures [11,17-18].

Besides thermal crystallization, the use of supercritical fluids to crystallize polymers has certain advantages. Since the activity of a SCF can be varied by controlling the pressure, SCFs can be effectively tuned to affect polymer morphology. An important advantage that SCFs have over liquid solvent crystallization is that SCFs can be removed simply through depressurization, whereas liquid solvents linger due to lower vapor pressure. Certain limitations do exist, however. At high pressures chain constraint due to hydrostatic pressure exerted by the fluid presents a limitation to the effectiveness of increasing pressure [19].

The ability to induce crystallinity in polymers by exposing the polymer to vapors has been studied [20], but a relative newcomer is the interaction of polymers with SCFs. Furthermore, solvent-induced crystallinity (SINC) of polymers using SCFs has been researched on commodity polymers such as PMMA [21], PET [22], polycarbonate [23], polystyrene [24], and blends of poly(vinylidene fluoride) and poly(methyl methacrylate) [25]. The plasticization caused by exposure of PEEK to supercritical CO₂ [26] has been reported. By annealing at various exposure time, pressure and temperature, changes result in the ratios of the two lamellae populations.

This research focuses on the effect that supercritical fluid solvent exposure has on the morphology of PEEK. The present study will address the possibility of crystallizing PEEK to different levels with supercritical fluids at different pressures and temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

SAMPLE PREPARATION

VICTREX PEEK 150 PG grade powder was obtained from ICI, Inc. This powder was first dried in a vacuum oven at 70° for 24 hours. It was then melted on a Carver hot press at 400°C with no pressure for three minutes. For the next 30 seconds, cyclic loading of 0-1000 pounds was used to remove any bubbles. Then pressure was released and the resulting film was quenched in an ice water bath to minimize crystallization. These amorphous films were aged in a vacuum oven for 66 hours at 133°C (10°C below T_g). The purpose of the aging is to relax the polymer to the equilibrium state. The films ranged in thickness from 0.15 to 0.20 mm.

SOLVENT SELECTION

Solvent selection was limited by the critical temperature of the solvents because of the desire to induce crystallinity at temperatures below the T_g listed for PEEK at atmospheric pressure. Most liquid solvents known to induce crystallinity in PEEK at ambient conditions were eliminated from testing because of high critical temperatures.

Argon, chlorodifluoromethane, fluoroform and propane were selected. Chlorodifluoromethane, hereafter referred to as R-22, has a critical temperature (T_c) of 96.2°C and a critical pressure (T_p) of 4.97 MPa (721 psi). Corresponding data are listed for argon, fluoroform and propane in Table 1. All solvents were used as received.

Table 1. Critical data of selected SCFs [27]

Solvent	Formula	T _c (°C)	P _c (MPa)
argon	Ar	122.4	4.87
chlorodifluoromethane	CHClF ₂	96.2	4.97
fluoroform	CHF ₃	26.2	4.86
propane	C ₃ H ₈	96.7	4.25

METHODS

Films were exposed to SCFs in a high pressure viewcell. Preliminary tests were performed on amorphous films to determine which solvents would induce crystallinity. Amorphous samples were used for the preliminary tests, as SINC could be visually observed as a change in opacity in these samples.

Specimens were placed in the viewcell. Solvent in liquid form was transferred from a pressure bomb to the cell. Heat was applied and controlled with heating tape and an Omega CN9000A temperature controller capable of $\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ resolution. Pressure was applied by hydraulically moving the piston at one end of the pressure vessel to reduce operating volume. Once the desired pressure was attained, it was maintained within ± 1.4 MPa (200 psi) for the duration of the experiment. Afterwards the pressure was released and the heater was turned off. Once the cell cooled enough to be handled, the samples were removed and weighed to determine any residual solvent. The use of chlorodifluoromethane resulted in the greatest weight gain. A confirming test carried out at 34.5 MPa (5,000 psi) and 110°C was run using argon to verify that the SCF R-22 induced crystallization was not due only to small molecule diffusion.

Amorphous films were then exposed to SCF R-22 at various pressures, temperatures and exposure times. Pressures ranged from 13.8 MPa (2,000 psi) to 41.4 MPa (6,000 psi). Temperatures were bracketed by the critical temperature of R-22 and the glass transition temperature of PEEK and ranged from 110 to 130°C. Exposure times varied from one to twenty hours.

Weight measurements were made on a Mettler AE 50 electronic balance with an accuracy of 10^{-4} gram. DSC measurements were made by a Mettler TC10A in a temperature range from 50-400 °C at a scan rate of 10 K/min. DSC and SAXS were run on samples to measure relative crystallinity differences due to the SCF solvent exposures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Selected DSC heating cycles of PEEK exposed to various SCF solvents are illustrated in Fig. 1. Residual weight uptake of R-22 was ten percent. All other solvents remained at less than one percent. Note that, in spite of relatively low absorption of propane, the cold crystallization curve of PEEK exposed to propane was almost completely erased, suggesting SINC. It is unclear whether the remaining exotherm is due to crystallization or solvent evolution upon heating above T_g. Such effects were not observed with fluorooform.

Argon was used in place of R-22 to isolate the effect of pressure from that of specific interactions. As expected for an element with virtually no reactivity, no changes are noted in PEEK's cold crystallization curve in the resulting DSC trace. This is further confirmation that SINC is not only a diffusion effect, but a result of specific interactions that lead to plasticization.

The crystallinity induced in PEEK upon exposure to SCFs was confirmed in the following manner. Visually, amorphous PEEK film is a transparent, light yellow. Film that has crystallized appreciably often turns opaque. This, of course, is a function of spherulite size and crystallinity level. Samples that did not turn opaque were further analyzed by DSC. The depression or disappearance of the initial cold crystallization peak during a heating cycle is further indication of crystallinity. Finally, small-angle x-ray scattering (SAXS) was used to verify lamellar spacing. For example, Fig. 2 is a SAXS scan of PEEK that has been exposed to R-22 at 41.37 MPa and 110°C for 20 hours. Long-spacing, calculated at 10 nm, is consistent with results found for thermally crystallized PEEK [28].

PEEK was exposed to SCF R-22 under a variety of conditions. Fig. 3 is a comparison of PEEK films exposed to different times and the same temperature and pressure. The DSC trace of the amorphous sample is included. Significant differences in the initial crystallization peak are evident. At two hours exposure, the crystallization peak and the T_g are diminished significantly.

Fig. 4 is a comparison of samples exposed for different pressures and the same temperature and time. The sample exposed at the lower pressure shows a small crystallization peak. The higher pressure shows the complete disappearance of the crystallization peak and T_g , again suggesting SINC.

Thermal analysis is consistent with SAXS results. Fig. 5 is a composite of scattering data from samples exposed for different temperatures and pressures. The sample exposed at the lowest temperature and for the shortest time shows negligible crystalline character.

FUTURE WORK

The interaction behavior between the solvent and amorphous PEEK will be addressed. The ability to crystallize PEEK with propane, CO₂ and chlorodifluoromethane reveal an interesting question regarding the ability of a nonpolar, a weak quadrupolar, and a polar solvent, respectively, to cause SINC in PEEK. In related work at Virginia Tech, PEEK films which had undergone crystallization and weight gain due to exposure to supercritical carbon dioxide returned to original weight after a resting period of 24 hours at ambient conditions, but chlorodifluoromethane was retained at a level of four percent [29]. Molecular modeling will be used to determine the extent and nature of the polymer and solvent interaction.

Mechanical performance is being measured on PEEK films which have been thermally and solvent crystallized to various degrees. Preliminary results show that exposure of thermally crystallized samples to SCF solvents further increases crystallinity. Resulting morphology is under investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

The objective of this experiment was to study the interaction of supercritical fluids with PEEK. The ability to control SINC in PEEK by varying pressure, temperature and time was illustrated.

Samples were prepared from PEEK powder and exposed to SCF chlorodifluoromethane, propane, and fluoroform. Weight uptake measurements showed that only chlorodifluoromethane was sorbed by PEEK to a significant degree. However, crystallinity was also induced by propane. SINC was shown to be controlled on a relative scale in PEEK as verified by DSC and SAXS.

The fact that SINC is a function of specific interactions and not of diffusion or molecular size alone was shown in two ways: argon did not induce crystallinity; propane, despite its larger size, did induce crystallinity.

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Figure 1. DSC curves of PEEK upon exposure to SCFs

Figure 2. SAXS of PEEK exposed to SCF R-22

Figure 3. DSC scans of PEEK exposed to SCF R-22 with varying time

Figure 4. DSC scans of PEEK exposed to SCF R-22 with varying pressure

Figure 5. SAXS of PEEK showing effect of exposure time and pressure on crystallinity

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